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4 **Hyaluronic acid of tailored molecular weight by enzymatic and**
5 **acid depolymerization.**
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24 **ABSTRACT**
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27 Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a glycosaminoglycan crucial for homeostasis of tissues, and its
28 role on cell signalling and regulation of tissue injury and repair largely depends on HA
29 molecular weight. Therefore, HA application in a variety of fields requires HA of defined
30 size. While a number of enzymatic, chemical and physical methods exist for HA
31 depolymerization, limited information is currently available for accurate planning of
32 experiments. In the present work, we propose a pseudo-mechanistic model to describe
33 depolymerization kinetics of HA with hyaluronidase, chondroitinase ABC and
34 phosphoric acid. Data to feed the model was provided by monitoring molecular weight
35 reduction by gel permeation chromatography with light scattering detection over 24 h.
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37 Five enzyme to substrate ratios and three temperatures were used for enzymatic and
38 chemical reactions respectively, allowing for selection of operational parameters in a
39 range of conditions. The model adequately reproduces the resulting data providing
40 flexibility in the planning of the reactions to obtain HA of the desired molecular weight.
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65 **Keywords:** Hyaluronic acid; enzymatic depolymerization; acid hydrolysis.
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68 **1. Introduction**

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70 Glycosaminoglycans are linear polysaccharides consisting of O-linked disaccharide
71 units endowed with a range of biological activities [1-3]. Within this group, hyaluronic
72 acid (HA) stands as the only non-sulfated representative, forming long chains of D-
73 glucuronic acid (GlcA) linked to N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (GlcNAc) through alternating
74 $\beta(1,3)$ and $\beta(1,4)$ glycosidic bonds. Despite its apparent simplicity, HA appears as a
75 critical component of the extracellular and pericellular matrices, regulating essential
76 cellular events such as adhesion, mobility, proliferation and differentiation [4, 5].
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80 More strikingly, HA displays antagonistic effects on certain biological functions, such as
81 inflammation, cell migration and proliferation [4]. Among other factors, these
82 contradictory effects can be explained by molecular weight size and distribution. High
83 molecular weight HA (>1 MDa) has been associated to wound healing, inflammation
84 suppression, protection of the epithelial tissue, tissue homeostasis, and antiproliferative
85 and antiangiogenic effects, while HA between 250 kDa and 1MDa appears as a pro-
86 inflammatory agent [6]. HA fragments of 117 kDa have shown to inhibit migration and
87 invasion of cancer cells, whereas 35 kDa produced the opposite effects [7]. Disruption
88 of the extracellular matrix homeostasis driven by cancer and oxidative stress seems to
89 occur along with increased concentrations of HA of less than 250 kDa and ultimately
90 oligomers. The latter are able to produce contrasting effects on inflammation, invasion,
91 angiogenesis and cell proliferation [6]. This serves to illustrate the importance of HA
92 chain length and the need for reliable methods to produce HA of defined molecular
93 weight.
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112 HA cannot be currently synthesized and must be obtained from animal tissue or by
113 bacterial fermentation of certain *Streptococci* species [8, 9]. Either way, the molecular
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119 weight of purified HA typically exceeds 1MDa, thus obtention of lower molecular weight
120 material requires depolymerization. In animals, HA fragmentation occurs through
121 enzymatic catalysis by hyaluronidases and free radicals [6], although *in vitro*
122 depolymerization is also possible with bacterial enzymes and by physicochemical
123 means [10]. Vertebrate hyaluronidases are endo- β -*N*-acetyl-hexosaminidases which
124 randomly hydrolyse $\beta(1\rightarrow4)$ glycosidic bonds [11]. In HA, they cleave GlcNAc-GlcA
125 linkages without modification of the polysaccharide structure. Some forms are also
126 active on chondroitin sulfate [12]. A number of works have described hydrolysis
127 kinetics of hyaluronidase on HA, defining reaction parameters generally based on
128 analysis of the oligosaccharides produced, i.e. by HPLC [13] or capillary
129 electrophoresis [14], or reducing end formation [15, 16]. More rarely, the reaction has
130 been followed by taking advantage of absolute molecular weight estimates provided by
131 gel permeation chromatography with light scattering detection (GPC-LS) [17]. These
132 studies have provided good insight into reaction mechanisms and kinetics, however
133 planning of depolymerization experiments is not straightforward based on the
134 information provided.

135 HA depolymerization with bacterial enzymes has not been so extensively described as
136 with vertebrate hyaluronidases, because the former degrade preferentially chondroitin
137 sulfate and dermatan sulfate [18]. Bacterial enzymes act as *N*-acetylhexosaminidases,
138 producing β -elimination across the $1\rightarrow4$ link which results in the formation of an
139 unsaturated bond between C-4 and C-5 of the acid sugar. Within this group,
140 chondroitinase ABC (CASE) from *Proteus vulgaris* is the most widely used for
141 glycosaminoglycan degradation [12]. CASE actually consists of two enzymes, an
142 endolyase (CASE-I) and an exolyase (CASE-II). CASE-I produces tetrasaccharides and
143 disaccharides as end products, while CASE-II acts processively from the non-reducing
144 end releasing disaccharides [19]. Enzymatic activity on HA has been described by
145 increase of absorption at 232 nm due to the formation of a double bond on the sugar
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180 acid [18, 19], but to the best of our knowledge the reaction has never been followed by
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182 GPC-LS.
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184 Physicochemical methods include acid and alkaline hydrolysis, ultrasonic and thermal
185 degradation, attack by oxidants and exposure to radiation of different types [10].
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188 Among these, acid hydrolysis appears as a cost effective method to depolymerise HA
189 [20]. The process produces random scission of glycosidic bonds preferentially at
190 $\beta(1\rightarrow4)$ links, although cleavage of $\beta(1\rightarrow3)$ bonds also occurs to a lesser extent [21,
191 22]. Temperature and pH have shown to influence kinetics of the reaction, generally
192 carried out with strong acids such as HCl [22, 23]. Rate constants and other kinetics
193 parameters have been calculated from these experiments, as well as from numerical
194 simulations applied to model the hydrolytic process [20]. However, as is the case for
195 enzymatic methods, design of depolymerization processes is not straightforward based
196 on the information provided.
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207 In the present work we propose to fill this gap by proposing a pseudo-mechanistic
208 model capable of predicting the conditions of reaction for the depolymerization of HA
209 with bovine testicular hyaluronidase (HASE), CASE, and phosphoric acid. To this end,
210 each reaction was followed by GPC-LS over 24 h, registering absolute molecular
211 weight at specific times. Enzymatic reactions were studied at four enzyme to substrate
212 ratios and acid hydrolysis at three different temperatures. This allows for selection of
213 operational parameters in a range of conditions, providing flexibility in the planning of
214 the reaction and ultimately enabling to obtain HA of the desired molecular weight.
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222 **2. Materials and methods**

223 *2.1. Depolymerization of hyaluronic acid*

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225 Hyaluronic acid (HA) was produced by microbial fermentation from *Streptococcus equi*
226 *subsp. zooepidemicus* ATCC 35246 according to the processes previously described
227 [24, 25]. Then, HA was isolated and purified from bacterial post-incubates by a
228 combination of chemical and ultrafiltration treatments [9] to obtain HA of purity greater
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239 than 98% and 1.2 MDa of molecular weight. This final HA was depolymerized with
240 chondroitinase ABC (CASE) from *Proteus vulgaris* (EC 4.2.2.4., 0.86 U mg⁻¹, Prod. No.
241 C2905, Sigma-Aldrich), hyaluronidase (HASE) from bovine testes type I-S (EC
242 3.2.1.35., 587 U mg⁻¹, Prod. No. H3506, Sigma-Aldrich), and phosphoric acid (85%,
243 Prod. No. 20624.295, VWR Chemicals). HA was dissolved at 1 g/L, in 50 mM TRIS-
244 HCl / 150 mM sodium acetate at pH 8 for reaction with CASE; in 5 mM NaH₂PO₄ / 150
245 mM NaCl at pH 4 for HASE depolymerization; and in ultrapure water for hydrolysis with
246 H₃PO₄. Enzymatic reactions were carried out in triplicate at 37°C under magnetic
247 stirring by adding the appropriate amounts of either enzyme to tubes containing 10 mL
248 of HA solutions to reach enzyme to substrate ratios of 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, 0.075 and
249 0.01 units of CASE and 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 7.0 and 12.0 units of HASE per mg of HA. At
250 various times, 0.6 mL aliquots were taken and reactions stopped by heating at 70°C for
251 25 min. After centrifugation at 15000g for 30 min, supernatants were filtered through
252 0.2 µm polyethersulfone (PES) membranes and stored at -20°C until analysis. Acid
253 hydrolysis was performed in duplicate after addition of 5 mg H₃PO₄ per mg HA
254 (pH=1.71) to 10 mL of 1 g/L HA solutions at 40 °C, 60 °C and 75 °C. At various times,
255 0.6 mL aliquots were taken, reactions stopped by neutralization with NaOH, filtered
256 through 0.2 µm PES membranes and stored at -20°C until analysis.

275 2.2. Molecular weight determination

276 Filtered samples were injected onto a GPC system (Agilent1260) consisting of
277 quaternary pump (G1311B), injector (G1329B), column oven (G1316A), refractive
278 index (G1362A) and dual angle static light scattering (G7800A) detectors.
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280 Chromatographic separation was carried out with a set of four Suprema columns (PSS,
281 Mainz, Germany): precolumn 5 µm, 8x50 mm; 30Å 5 µm, 8x300 mm; 100Å 5 µm,
282 8x300 mm; and ultrahigh 10 µm, 8x300 mm. A sample volume of 100 µl was injected
283 onto the system and eluted at a flow rate of 1 mL/min with 0.1 M NaN₃ and 0.01 M
284 NaH₂PO₄ at pH 6.6. Column oven and light scattering detector were kept at 30°C, while
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298 refractive index detector was maintained at 40°C. Both detectors were calibrated with a
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300 polyethylene oxide standard (PSS, Mainz, Germany) of 106 kDa (Mw) and
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302 polydispersity index (PDI) 1.05, dissolved in the mobile phase at 1g/L. Absolute
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304 molecular weights were determined combining refractive index and dual angle light
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306 scattering signals using refractive index increments (dn/dc) of 0.150.
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308 309 2.3. Depolymerization modelling and estimation 310

311 Enzymatic depolymerization kinetics follows the next expression:
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$$313 \frac{dM_n}{dt} = -k(M_n - M_n^*)^n \quad (1)$$

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315 where M_n is the number average molecular weight of HA (in Da), n is the kinetic order
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317 (dimensionless), k the rate of decay (in h⁻¹) and M_n^* the molecular weight after
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319 depolymerization for 24 h (in Da). The enzyme to substrate ratio (E) affects both the
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321 kinetic rate and the molecular weight after depolymerization for 24h, and was modeled
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323 with the following expressions:
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$$330 k(E) = \frac{V_m E}{K_m + E} \quad (2)$$

$$331 M_n^*(E) = M_n^e e^{-\mu E} \quad (3)$$

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333 where V_m is the maximum reaction rate (in h⁻¹), K_m the Michaelis-Menten constant (in U
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335 mg⁻¹), μ a coefficient of fitting (in mg U⁻¹) and M_n^e denotes the estimated initial
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337 molecular weight (in Da). There are four parameters (V_m , K_m , M_n^e and μ) that are
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339 unknown a priori, but can be estimated from depolymerization data with, at least, two
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341 levels of enzyme.
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357 For acid hydrolysis, eq. (2) assumes the form of Arrhenius equation, whose substitution
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359 in (1) at $n=2$ results in:

$$\frac{dM_n}{dt} = -Ae^{-\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)} (M_n - M_n^d)^2 \quad (4)$$

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362 where M_n^d is the molecular weight of a saturated disaccharide (397.3 Da), A the pre-
363 exponential factor (in $\text{Da}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$), R the Universal gas constant ($0.0083145 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T
364 the absolute temperature (in K) and E_a the activation energy (in kJ mol^{-1}).
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367 For the estimation of the parameters we minimized the residual sum of squares with
368 the AMIGO2 toolbox [26]. For the implementation, we used an estimation protocol
369 previously described [27] with the derivative form of expression (1).
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373 374 375 376 377 378 379 380 **3. Results and discussion**

381 382 *3.1. Molecular weight distribution profiles*

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384 Fig. 1 illustrates the decrease in molecular weight during enzymatic and chemical
385 depolymerization of HA monitored by GPC-LS. In all cases, the distributions shift
386 toward lower retention volumes as reaction time increases, consistent with a reduction
387 in molecular weight. In the process, peak heights of the depolymerized fragments
388 decrease compared to original HA, especially in enzymatic hydrolysis, but areas of the
389 distributions remain virtually unchanged in acid and HASE hydrolyses, consistent with
390 random cleavage. In the case of CASE, the reaction not only widens the distributions
391 but also diminishes their area. This agrees with the -exo action of CASE, as
392 disaccharides stripped off the chain do not remain in the main HA distribution and
393 typically appear as a single peak at higher retention volumes [18, 19]. Increases in the
394 disaccharide peak may give an indication on the extent of the -exo action. In our case,
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Figure 1. Illustrative GPC eluograms (refractive index detector signals) of hyaluronic acid (HA) from *S. zooepidemicus* depolymerized with (A) hyaluronidase (12 U/mg HA), (B) chondroitinase ABC (0.1 U/mg HA), and (C) phosphoric acid (1:5 w/w; 75°C) at different reaction times.

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475 can still be evaluated by the variation in the area of the main polymeric peak as
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477 molecular weight decreases (Fig. 2). We have fitted the data represented by the
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479 following expression:
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$$A = M_n^0 (1 - e^{-0.0188(M_w - 27.6792)})$$

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485 Where A is the refractive index area of the HA peak measured by GPC and M_n^0 the
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487 initial molecular weight. The fitting is reasonably good, with R_{adj} of 0.7010. The model
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489 displays a near-zero slope from original HA down to around 300 kDa, indicating
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491 predominant –endo action. From this value downwards the slope dramatically
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493 increases as random cleavage is replaced by the processive mechanism, possibly
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495 because of diminished aggregation of HA [11]. In practical terms, this implicates
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497 minimal loss of HA mass down to around 300 kDa. As peak area is directly related to
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499 HA mass, we can estimate the mass of HA released as disaccharides using the above
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501 model, resulting for example in losses of 0.3% at 400 kDa, 1.2% at 300 kDa, 5.3% at
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503 100 kDa and 23.1% at 100 kDa.
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523 **Figure 2.** Area of the main HA peak (GPC – refractive index detector) versus estimated
524 molecular weight (M_n) for CASE depolymerization (scatter). Solid line represents the fitting
525 model.
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3.2. Depolymerization kinetics

In all experiments reduction of molecular weight was more pronounced at the start of the reaction (Fig. 3). In enzymatic digestions, the decrease is very slight after 5-6 hours, reaching an almost static state. Hence, we considered depolymerization after 24 h as the final point of the enzymatic reactions, even though they could theoretically progress to lower molecular weight oligosaccharides and disaccharides [18, 28]. In acid

Figure 3. Evolution of number average molecular weight (M_n) of HA during depolymerization reactions with (a) chondroitinase and (b) hyaluronidase at five enzyme to substrate ratios and (c) phosphoric acid (5:1 w/w) at three temperatures. Model solution represented by solid lines; scatter data: average M_n (kDa) at each sampling time; error bars: standard deviation (n=3 for HASE and CASE; n=2 for phosphoric acid).

hydrolysis, this phenomenon does not appear. Because at the reaction pH (1.7) cleavage occurs preferentially at the $\beta(1\rightarrow4)$ glycosidic bond between GlcNAc and

GlcA [22], the lowest molecular weight for the enzymatic reaction was set to 397.3 Da (saturated disaccharide)

The model proves capable of reproducing the experimental data within the enzyme to substrate ratios, temperatures and timeframes defined, as shown in Fig. 3. In enzymatic digestions, reaction rate was left free in the model, resulting in reaction rates of 1.83 for CASE and 2.70 for HASE (Table 1), while in acid hydrolysis, reaction rate was set to 2 [22]. Among the model parameters shown in Tables 1 and 2, adjusted correlation coefficients of 0.986 for CASE, 0.991 for HASE and 0.978 for acid hydrolysis demonstrate the goodness of fit of the model.

	V_m	K_m	μ	n	M_n^e	R_{adj}^2
CASE	7.36×10^{-5}	0.019036	39.5139	1.8305	645878	0.9862
HASE	6.62×10^{-4}	5×10^5	0.82979	2.6913	565542	0.9907

Table 1. Fitting parameters (M_n) of enzymatic depolymerization of HA.

	A	E_a	M_n^d	R_{adj}^2
	1.381×10^8	91.693	365.8	0.9780

Table 2. Fitting parameters (M_n) of acid depolymerization of HA. E_a in kJ mol^{-1} ; A in $\text{Da}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$; M_n^e in Da.

In enzymatic reactions we assumed that the enzyme to substrate ratio (E) affected the kinetic rate (k) and the molecular weight after depolymerization for 24h (M_n^*). A

Michaelis-Menten adjustment for k proved adequate (2), and dependence of M_n^* with E was modeled with a negative exponential equation (3), as linear or second order polynomials produced worse fits.

In acid hydrolysis, k was estimated using the Arrhenius equation, with values for pre-exponential factor (A) and activation energy (E_a) of $1.38 \times 10^{11} \text{ kDa}^{-1} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and 91.7 kJ mol^{-1}

1 respectively (Table 2). Although to the authors' knowledge, HA hydrolysis with phosphoric acid has not been previously reported, E_a of 137 kJ mol⁻¹ was estimated for HA depolymerization with 0.1 M HCl [22]. To determine the source of the discrepancy, we can use the same calculation method applied in [22] for our data. This method consists in a linear regression applied to the log-transformed Arrhenius equation, with kinetic rate constants previously determined by linearization of a second order kinetic equation. As a result, we obtain a much closer value of 133 kJ mol⁻¹. The difference seems then to arise from the double linearization applied. In fact, fitting of the molecular weight data with 133 kJ mol⁻¹ achieves R_{adj}^2 of 0.893, compared to 0.978 obtained when parameters are jointly estimated, which indicates the suitability of the method presented here.

3.2. Design of depolymerization experiments

The proposed model allows to define the conditions of reaction required to obtain HA of the molecular weight desired. Fig. 4 depicts the possible combinations of E and reaction time for enzymatic depolymerization, and temperature and reaction time for acid hydrolysis, as a function of M_n . As can be seen, a given M_n can be reached by increased t at low E (or T) or vice versa. Reaction times at chosen E and T can be calculated integrating differential equation (1):

$$\frac{1}{(M_n - M_n^*)^{n-1}} = \frac{1}{(M_n^0 - M_n^*)^{n-1}} + (n-1)kt \quad (5)$$

Where

$$t = \left(\frac{1}{(n-1)k} \right) \left(\frac{1}{(M_n - M_n^*)^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{(M_n^0 - M_n^*)^{n-1}} \right)$$

For enzymatic depolymerization, substituting relationships (2) and (3) in (5):

Figure 4. Variation in Mn of HA with reaction time and (a,b) enzyme to substrate ratio (E) and (c) temperature (T) .

$$t = \left(\frac{K_m + E}{V_m E(n-1)} \right) \left(\frac{1}{(M_n - M_w^e e^{-\mu E})^{n-1}} - \frac{1}{(M_n^0 - M_n^e e^{-\mu E})^{n-1}} \right) \quad (6)$$

For chemical hydrolysis, substituting relationship (4) in (5):

$$t = A e^{-\left(\frac{Ea}{RT}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{M_n - M_n^d} - \frac{1}{M_n^0 - M_n^d} \right) \quad (7)$$

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773 Where M_n^0 is the initial molecular weight. When selecting particular reaction conditions
774
775 it must be born in mind that shortening reaction times by increasing E or T results in a
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777 more abrupt decrease of M_n . Stopping the reaction under these conditions may
778
779 compromise M_n accuracy, as small variations in time can result in large changes in M_n .
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781 This is particularly relevant for enzymatic reactions since inactivation of the enzymes
782
783 by heat is not instantaneous and may pose operational challenges at large scale.
784
785 Besides accuracy, other aspects may influence the selection of a particular reaction.
786
787 Phosphoric acid may represent an interesting option because of its low cost compared
788
789 to enzymes, but only down to medium-sized HA, as either high temperature or long
790
791 reaction times are required to achieve low molecular weight fragments. For the latter,
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793 enzymatic depolymerization may represent a better option. CASE is considerably more
794
795 expensive than HASE, has less affinity for HA and as already discussed, the yield of
796
797 depolymerized CS decreases dramatically below 300 kDa because of disaccharide
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799 stripping by the –exo form. Therefore, HASE may appear as a more attractive option
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801 for enzymatic depolymerization. On the other hand, the chemical structure of
802
803 depolymerized HA products may be of great importance. HASE preserves the chemical
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805 structure of undepolymerized HA, whereas CASE yields reaction products carrying
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807 unsaturation at the non-reducing end. For detection purposes, this is an advantage as
808
809 unsaturation allows HA to absorb UV radiation. In other applications, the possibly
810
811 altered bioactivity introduced in HA by such structural changes may pose a problem, as
812
813 it might trigger immune reactions, or represent an advantage for materials more
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815 resilient to biogenic degradation.

816 817 **4. Conclusions**

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819 We have described the depolymerization of hyaluronic acid with hyaluronidase,
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821 chondroitinase and phosphoric acid through a pseudo-mechanistic model. Good fits
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829 are obtained with adjusted correlation coefficients greater than 0.978 in all cases. The
830
831 proposed equations allow to define combinations of enzyme amount and reaction time,
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833 or temperature and reaction time for acid hydrolysis, to obtain HA of the desired
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835 molecular weight.
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838 **Conflict of interest**

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840 The authors declare no conflict of interest.
841

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855 **References**

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857
858 [1] J. Valcarcel, R. Novoa-Carballal, R.I. Pérez-Martín, R.L. Reis, J.A. Vázquez,
859 Glycosaminoglycans from marine sources as therapeutic agents, *Biotechnol. Adv.*
860 35(6) (2017) 711-725.
861
862 [2] D. Soares da Costa, R.L. Reis, I. Pashkuleva, Sulfation of Glycosaminoglycans and
863 Its Implications in Human Health and Disorders, *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.* 19(1)
864 (2017).
865
866 [3] V.H. Pomin, A Dilemma in the Glycosaminoglycan-Based Therapy: Synthetic or
867 Naturally Unique Molecules?, *Med. Res. Rev.* 35(6) (2015) 1195-1219.
868
869 [4] S. Garantziotis, R.C. Savani, Hyaluronan biology: A complex balancing act of
870 structure, function, location and context, *Matrix Biol.* 78-79 (2019) 1-10.
871
872 [5] J. Liang, D. Jiang, P.W. Noble, Hyaluronan as a therapeutic target in human
873 diseases, *Adv. Drug Del. Rev.* 97 (2016) 186-203.
874
875 [6] A.G. Tavianatou, I. Caon, M. Franchi, Z. Piperigkou, D. Galesso, N.K. Karamanos,
876 Hyaluronan: molecular size-dependent signaling and biological functions in
877 inflammation and cancer, *The FEBS journal* 0(0).
878
879 [7] Y.-f. Zhao, S.-p. Qiao, S.-l. Shi, L.-f. Yao, X.-l. Hou, C.-f. Li, F.-H. Lin, K. Guo, A.
880 Acharya, X.-b. Chen, Y. Nie, W.-m. Tian, Modulating Three-Dimensional
881 Microenvironment with Hyaluronan of Different Molecular Weights Alters Breast Cancer
882 Cell Invasion Behavior, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* 9(11) (2017) 9327-9338.
883
884 [8] J.A. Vázquez, I. Rodríguez-Amado, M. Montemayor, J. Fraguas, M. González, M.Á.
885 Murado, Chondroitin sulfate, hyaluronic acid and chitin/chitosan production using
marine waste sources: Characteristics, applications and eco-friendly processes: A
review, *Mar. Drugs* 11(3) (2013) 747.

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941
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- [9] M.A. Murado, M.I. Montemayor, M. Cabo, J.A. Vázquez, M. González, Optimization of extraction and purification process of hyaluronic acid from fish eyeball, *Food Bioprod. Process.* 90(3) (2012) 491-498.
- [10] R. Stern, G. Kogan, M.J. Jedrzejewski, L. Šoltés, The many ways to cleave hyaluronan, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 25(6) (2007) 537-557.
- [11] R. Stern, M.J. Jedrzejewski, Hyaluronidases: their genomics, structures, and mechanisms of action, *Chem. Rev.* 106(3) (2006) 818-839.
- [12] J.W. Wenshuang Wang, Fuchuan Li, *Protein Reviews Volume 17*, Springer 2017.
- [13] J.A. Cramer, L.C. Bailey, C.A. Bailey, R.T. Miller, Kinetic and mechanistic studies with bovine testicular hyaluronidase, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) - General Subjects* 1200(3) (1994) 315-321.
- [14] S. Fayad, R. Nehmé, M. Langmajerová, B. Ayela, C. Colas, B. Maunit, J.-C. Jacquinet, A. Vibert, C. Lopin-Bon, G. Zdeněk, P. Morin, Hyaluronidase reaction kinetics evaluated by capillary electrophoresis with UV and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) detection, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 951 (2017) 140-150.
- [15] T. Astériou, J.-C. Vincent, F. Tranchepain, B. Deschrevel, Inhibition of hyaluronan hydrolysis catalysed by hyaluronidase at high substrate concentration and low ionic strength, *Matrix Biol.* 25(3) (2006) 166-174.
- [16] B. Deschrevel, F. Tranchepain, J.-C. Vincent, Chain-length dependence of the kinetics of the hyaluronan hydrolysis catalyzed by bovine testicular hyaluronidase, *Matrix Biol.* 27(5) (2008) 475-486.
- [17] F. Tranchepain, B. Deschrevel, M.-N. Courel, N. Levasseur, D. Le Cerf, C. Loutelier-Bourhis, J.-C. Vincent, A complete set of hyaluronan fragments obtained from hydrolysis catalyzed by hyaluronidase: Application to studies of hyaluronan mass distribution by simple HPLC devices, *Anal. Biochem.* 348(2) (2006) 232-242.
- [18] T. Yamagata, H. Saito, O. Habuchi, S. Suzuki, Purification and Properties of Bacterial Chondroitinases and Chondrosulfatases, *J. Biol. Chem.* 243(7) (1968) 1523-1535.
- [19] A. Hamai, N. Hashimoto, H. Mochizuki, F. Kato, Y. Makiguchi, K. Horie, S. Suzuki, Two distinct chondroitin sulfate ABC lyases: An endoeliminase yielding tetrasaccharides and an exoeliminase preferentially acting on oligosaccharides, *J. Biol. Chem.* 272(14) (1997) 9123-9130.
- [20] A.A. Martens, N.A.M. Besseling, S. Rueb, E.J.R. Sudhölter, H.P. Spaink, L.C.P.M. de Smet, Random Scission of Polymers: Numerical Simulations, and Experiments on Hyaluronan Hydrolysis, *Macromolecules* 44(8) (2011) 2559-2567.
- [21] Y. Inoue, K. Nagasawa, Preparation, by chemical degradation of hyaluronic acid, of a series of even- and odd-numbered oligosaccharides having a 2-acetamido-2-deoxy-d-glucose and a d-glucuronic acid residue, respectively, at the reducing end, *Carbohydr. Res.* 141(1) (1985) 99-110.
- [22] K. Tømmeraas, C. Melander, Kinetics of Hyaluronan Hydrolysis in Acidic Solution at Various pH Values, *Biomacromolecules* 9(6) (2008) 1535-1540.
- [23] Y. Tokita, A. Okamoto, Hydrolytic degradation of hyaluronic acid, *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 48(2) (1995) 269-273.
- [24] J.A. Vázquez, M.I. Montemayor, J. Fraguas, M.A. Murado, Hyaluronic acid production by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* in marine by-products media from mussel processing wastewaters and tuna peptone viscera, *Microbial Cell Factories* 9(1) (2010) 46.
- [25] J.A. Vázquez, L. Pastrana, C. Piñeiro, J.A. Teixeira, R.I. Pérez-Martín, I.R. Amado, Production of hyaluronic acid by *Streptococcus zooepidemicus* on protein substrates obtained from *Scylliorhinus canicula* discards, *Mar. Drugs* 13(10) (2015) 6537-6549.

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[26] E. Balsa-Canto, D. Henriques, A. Gábor, J.R. Banga, AMIGO2, a toolbox for dynamic modeling, optimization and control in systems biology, *Bioinformatics* 32(21) (2016) 3357-3359.

[27] C. Vilas, A. Arias-Méndez, M.R. García, A.A. Alonso, E. Balsa-Canto, Toward predictive food process models: A protocol for parameter estimation, *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 58(3) (2018) 436-449.

[28] I. Kakizaki, N. Ibori, K. Kojima, M. Yamaguchi, M. Endo, Mechanism for the hydrolysis of hyaluronan oligosaccharides by bovine testicular hyaluronidase, *The FEBS journal* 277(7) (2010) 1776-1786.

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